

 indena[®]
INDUSTRIA
DERIVATI
NATURALI

PERSONAL CARE

CENTELLA ASIATICA

AND DERIVATIVES

The ingredients described herein are offered for consideration for use in personal care products. The information provided describes historical use, ingredient activity and other information that may be relevant to their use in such products. How each ingredient would contribute to a particular product would be formulation specific. Furthermore please note that this documentation is available for various countries all over the world and hence it may contain statements not applicable to your country.

The tender leaf of *Centella asiatica*, a spontaneous herbaceous plant also known as Gotu kola or Indian Pennyworth, is collected from Madagascar and contains several active molecules endowed with biological activity both for topical and oral applications. The most characteristic chemical compounds are the triterpenes as **asiaticoside**, **asiatic acid**, **madecassoside** and **madecassic acid**, but several biologically active polyphenols are also present in the leaf.

- Since ancient times, *Centella asiatica* has been traditionally used in Indian and Chinese medicine for various disorders, in particular for healing wounds. It is from Madagascar that Indena has selected the best *Centella asiatica* quality. Co-financing opportunities are also available for centella derivatives users willing to share Indena's sustainable approach.

CENDEVITA™

CHARACTERISTICS

HPLC CONTENT	≥45.0% of the sum of asiaticoside, madecassoside, asiatic acid and madecassic acid. Polyphenols for information only.
FORM	greenish powder
LEVEL OF USE	0.1 – 1%
SOLUBILITY*	soluble in alcohol 50° (v/v), slightly soluble in water, propylene glycol, glycerin
INCI/CTFA	centella asiatica leaf extract

PLUS

- ECOCERT VALIDATED
- COMBINATION OF ALL FOUR TERPENOIDS INCLUDING MADECASSOSIDE
- BIOACTIVE POLYPHENOLS
- PROMOTION OF COLLAGEN TYPE I AND III SYNTHESIS
- VALIDATED AS ANTI-GLYCATION AND ANTI-INFLAMMAGING
- SPECIFICALLY TAYLORED FOR PRODUCTS WITH A GREEN CLAIM

MADECASSOSIDE

CHARACTERISTICS

HPLC CONTENT	≥95.0 of madecassoside and terminolside
FORM	white / off white powder
LEVEL OF USE	0.1 – 0.5%
SOLUBILITY*	soluble in water and ethanol
INCI/CTFA	madecassoside

PLUS

- PURE MOLECULE
- PROMOTION OF COLLAGEN TYPE III SYNTHESIS
- WATER SOLUBLE

CENTEROX™

CHARACTERISTICS

HPLC CONTENT	≥50.0% ≤70.0% of madecassoside and terminolside, ≥10.0% ≤20.0% of asiaticoside, ≥70.0% ≤90.0% of sum of madecassoside, terminolside and asiaticoside
FORM	off white powder
LEVEL OF USE	0.1 – 0.5%
SOLUBILITY*	freely soluble in water, ethanol 50° (v/v), soluble in propylene glycol and glycerin
INCI/CTFA	madecassoside ^[A] , asiaticoside ^[B]

PLUS

- FREELY WATER SOLUBLE
- COMBINATION OF GLYCOSILATED TERPENOIDS
- PROMOTION OF COLLAGEN TYPE I AND III SYNTHESIS

ASIATICOSIDE

CHARACTERISTICS

HPLC CONTENT	≥85.0 of asiaticoside
FORM	white powder
LEVEL OF USE	0.1 – 0.5%
SOLUBILITY*	very soluble in propylene glycol, ethoxydiglycol, ethoxydiglycol / water (w/w 1:1); soluble in ethanol 50° (v/v), glycerin, butylene glycol, polyethylene glycol 400, polyethylene glycol 600
INCI/CTFA	asiaticoside

PLUS

- PURE MOLECULE
- PROMOTION OF COLLAGEN TYPE I SYNTHESIS
- SPECIFIC FOCUS AS ANTI-WRINKLE AGENT, CLINICALLY VALIDATED ON LIPS

CENTELLA ASIATICA SELECTED TRITERPENES

CHARACTERISTICS

HPLC CONTENT	≥36.0 ≤44.0% of asiaticoside, ≥56 ≤64.0% of genins as a sum of asiatic acid and madecassic acid
FORM	white powder
LEVEL OF USE	0.1 – 1%
SOLUBILITY*	soluble in propylene glycol, ethoxydiglycol, polyethylenglicol 600, polyoxyethylene sorbitan monooleate
INCI/CTFA	asiaticoside ^[A] , asiatic acid ^[B] , madecassic acid ^[C]

PLUS

- COMBINATION OF PURE TERPENOIDS
- HIGH CONCENTRATION OF BIOACTIVE COMPONENTS
- PROMOTION OF COLLAGEN TYPE I SYNTHESIS
- ALSO AVAILABLE IN PHARMACEUTICAL GRADE (DMF)

CENTELLA ASIATICA SELECTED TRITERPENES PHYTOSOME®

CHARACTERISTICS

HPLC CONTENT	≥30.0 ≤35.0% of selected triterpenes
FORM	yellow powder
LEVEL OF USE	0.1 – 1%
SOLUBILITY*	soluble in ethoxydiglycol at 40-50 °C (50 mg in 10 g of solvent)
INCI/CTFA	lecithin (syn phosphatidylcholine), asiaticoside, asiatic acid, madecassic acid

PLUS

- ENHANCED BIOAVAILABILITY
- COMBINATION OF PURE TERPENOIDS
- HIGH CONCENTRATION OF BIOACTIVE COMPONENTS
- PROMOTION OF COLLAGEN TYPE I SYNTHESIS

PHYTOSOME [®]
 MORE
 BIOAVAILABLE

*solubility is defined according to EP

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